

THERE IS NO SUCH THING AS A COMPOSITE MATERIAL – ONLY COMPOSITES *OF* MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The intent of this article is to provoke serious discussions about continued use of over-simplified homogenized-ply models for fibre/polymer composites, rather than the necessary but more complex models predicting failure at the individual-constituent level (discrete fibres and resin matrix). A choice between the two approaches to predicting laminate strengths became possible with the development of the SIFT (Strain Invariant Failure Theory) model in 2001. This provided a science-based, rather than purely empirical, method for predicting possible separate failure mechanisms (distortion and dilatation) in individual constituents, as well as a practical computerized code and simple look-up charts relating lamina-level strains to those in the individual constituents. The key issue is shown to be that weak soft resins have a very limited capability to transfer loads in and out of the strong stiff fibres, or between plies. The key adverse consequence of the never-justified assumption of homogeneity is shown here to be that the inability to accurately predict premature matrix failures during the initial design stage has caused long program delays, resulting in certification by costly full-scale testing. The need for redesign was sometimes not detected until series production was underway. It is shown that there are substantial previously unrecognized opportunities for major cost savings and improved composite structures from proper recognition that composites are heterogeneous, not homogeneous, and that the inevitably weak resin interfaces between plies impose design constraints that should not be concealed by omitting the interfaces from the models being analyzed.

1 INTRODUCTION AND EXPLANATION OF THE PROBLEM

In the world of fibre/polymer composites, no single decision has done more to impede development and implementation of reliable procedures for the analysis, design and manufacture of composite structures than promoting the notion that distinctly *heterogeneous* combinations of strong stiff fibres and weak soft polymer matrices could be characterized realistically as *homogeneous* orthotropic single-phase materials – for strength predictions, rather than only stiffnesses. The issue is not just the need to be able to predict matrix failures quickly and reliably. Failure to acknowledge the existence of separate fibre and matrix constituents frequently leads to inferior designs, and often to program delays and cost overruns in development and series production. If a material were truly homogeneous, it would be impossible for there to be internal residual stresses and strains in the absence of external mechanical loads. This is explained in Figure 1 for a unidirectional fibre/polymer composite ply, showing how the resin matrix tries to shrink after curing at high temperature, but is prevented from doing so by the embedded strong stiff fibres. Residual thermal stresses *within* each ply are real!

During cool-down after curing at high temperature, the resin tries to shrink around the fibres, but can't, so the fibres are compressed radially by the tensile hoop stresses developed in the resin matrix surrounding them. These stresses and strains are intensified by operating aircraft in the extremely cold upper atmosphere. Likewise, the resin tries to shrink along the length of the fibres, which resist even more strongly than through their thickness. This restraint creates large residual tensile stresses in the resin matrix, along the length of the fibres. The existence of these internal stresses is effectively denied by the assumption that each unidirectional ply, in isolation, behaves as if it were truly homogeneous.

Figure. 1 Shrinkage of resin matrix around fibres

So widespread has been this misconception that very few workers in this field recognize artificial homogenization as the source of so many unanticipated problems. One of the consequences of this never-justified mathematical simplifying assumption is the inability to predict failures in the matrix that precede failures in the fibres, which carry virtually the entire load, thereby reducing the structural efficiency of the composite laminates. No publication was ever prepared to demonstrate that essentially the same results were predicted with and without this approximation, which is an essential step in the process of validating the use of *any* analytical simplification.

Another consequence of the presumed homogenization is that wrinkles in the fibres caused by over-complicated high-cost co-cured structures that cause significant loss of strength are not even regarded as defects, unless they are so severe as to cause voids or porosity so great that they can be detected by standard ultrasonic non-destructive inspection techniques.

In addition, the presumption of homogeneity has distracted attention away from the critical need to pay attention to eliminating poor design details that do not prevent any primary loads from being transmitted entirely through a layer of resin by redesign *before* drawings are released, because it is too late to eliminate the problem later. Some real-life examples of problems that have arisen because of the misconception that fibre/polymer composites really are homogeneous might indicate the need to be more aware of their inherent heterogeneity in future. The two most frequent design defects in composite structures are illustrated in Figure 2. Sadly, both are usually regarded as desirable design assets, because the heterogeneous nature of fibre/polymer composites is so widely over-looked.

The stiffener run-out shown in Figure 2 is a very common design defect (for metallic structures as well as composite ones) because it lacks a direct load-path for the stiffener across the load path. It is portrayed as a desirable concept because it simplifies the design and installation of the splice plate (not shown) and “eliminates” the need for all the detail parts needed to carry the load between stiffeners on each side of the splice by transferring the load out of the stiffener ahead of the splice and into the skin (which is sometimes reinforced). It is then assumed, without analytical corroboration, that the tapered run-out will spread the load transfer gently over a long length. Proper analysis, however, shows that most of the load remains in the web of the stiffener remains in the web and is dumped out at the point X, delaminating the skin there. This condition is aggravated by the other common design defect shown, the 0-deg. noodle of fibers at the base of the stiffener web, which is considered to be a benefit because it increases the strength and stiffness of the stringer along its length. The problem is that the weak resin matrix does not allow the end load in the noodle to be transferred into the surrounding composite material. The load in the noodle is proportional to its cross section, while the ability of the surrounding resin is proportional only to the perimeter. Thus the severity of this problem is

proportional to its size. Worse, it intensifies the load causing the skin delaminations at the end of the stiffener.

Figure 2 The two most common design defects in fibre/polymer composite structures

Another common design error that is often overlooked concerns the blocking together of too many parallel unidirectional plies. This can lead to internal delaminations, as described in Figure 3. This was meant to have been a test to measure the strength of a bolted scarf joint, which would naturally have been far less than that of an equivalent unnotched laminate. However, it failed prematurely in the stepped-lap bonded load introduction fitting which had been believed to be far stronger than the bolted joint being tested, based on a typical analysis that checked for possible adhesive failures but omitted the calculation of the internal matrix stresses. The coupon failed in the load introduction area because the end step was far too thick. Consequently, the load transferred into the end step by the composite adjacent to its faces (Points A) was intensified by the added load that couldn't pass through the resin to the end of the stepped plate at Point B. The visible delaminations at Point D (and on the other side) were within the composite, not the adhesive. Had the initial failure been through the first bolt, it would have extended right through the laminate, staying well clear of the stepped-lap bonded joint, which is what was expected.

The weaknesses shown in Figure 2 have also occurred in less obvious situations. Figure 4 shows a composite fuselage skin on a military fighter aircraft stiffened by open-ended co-cured hollow hat stiffeners that were interrupted to allow the frame to be bolted to the inside of the skin without needing the usual mouse-holes in the outer portion of the frame to pass through uninterrupted. The interruptions were also needed to extract the rubber mandrels that defined the shape of the stiffener segments, because of the decision to reduce the part count. Discrete stringer segments do not count as separate parts if they are co-cured rather than made as separate details that are secondarily bonded, despite the enormous increase in recurring manufacturing cost incurred by the complexity of the co-cured design. The problems incurred by the innumerable interruptions in the stiffener load paths were then aggravated by moving most of the circumferential fibres as possible out of the frame flange into the skin, under each frame, to reduce the shear loads in the bolts connecting the frames to the skin. The net result from all of these anticipated cost reductions was that the skin where the stringer segment end loads were dumped into it was extremely rich in 90-deg. fibres (using the 0-deg. reference as the longitudinal axis of the stringers), as shown. Under load, the skin delaminated on both sides of every

frame at every skin layout, as shown on the right side of Figure 4. The design change made to eliminate the delaminations without needing to make new tools or to drastically change the drawings was to increase the recurring manufacturing cost even further by making the composite parts the same way in the same tools, but inserting a separator ply between the skin and the stringers that allowed the stringer segments to be bolted in place with about 30 bolts per segment. At least the bolts eliminated the intense interlaminar peel stresses developed because of the co-cured design. (They wouldn't have done so if the stringer segments were still bonded.)

Figure 3 Premature failure of stepped-lap bonded joint by delamination

Figure 4 Skin delaminations caused by segmenting co-cured composite stringers, and a possible design solution to the problem

Once the design error, to compromise the structural design to make a co-cured structure, had been committed to production, the opportunities to eliminate the problem on the right side of Figure 4

without incurring substantial non-recurring cost were severely limited. The suggestion on the left side of Figure 4 would have been far less expensive than the one actually implemented, because it required far fewer fasteners. Its key feature is to spread out the load transfer near the end of each stringer segment, because fasteners are far less stiff than resin matrices or adhesive bonds, so that the transfer of the stringer end loads was no longer concentrated right at their very ends. This suggested concept is equally applicable to uninterrupted stringers on aircraft wings or tails, if they are co-bonded or adhesively bonded. The bolts in the absence of any bond there also eliminate the severe peel stresses there.

A structurally far superior design alternative that could have been used in place of that described above, if only the initial focus had been on reducing the recurring manufacturing cost instead of the part count, enables both longitudinal and transverse load paths to be uninterrupted at the frame/stringer intersections is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Simple composite frame/stringer intersection with no loss of axial continuity in either member

There are no locations in which there are intense local loads in the resin matrix. The design relies on secondarily bonding pre-cured stringers to pre-cured skins and then bolting the stiffened skin to the frames. The purpose of showing the design in Figure 5 is to emphasize the point that, even though the resin matrix is very weak in comparison with the fibres, by paying attention to their heterogeneity, it is possible to create low-cost composite designs that are *not* limited by this weakness.

More details of the stiffener in Figure 5 are shown in Figure 6.

Even in this simple detail part, the manufacturing process was made compatible with the structural requirement for reinforcing at the cross-over points. Mechanical tests of stiffened flat panels made this way failed consistently in the middle of each segment, with the fibres attaining their full strengths. The stiffener design in Figure 6 was first applied on the all-composite LearFan commuter aircraft [1-2]. It has since been used very successfully on the tail cone of a large transport aircraft to solve a production problem with a co-cured initial design very similar to that shown in Figure 4, but without the reinforced skin, in which the initial production problems were *so* severe, and so costly, that the tail cone was totally redesigned and retooled to be secondarily bonded from simple defect-free skins and stiffeners at a cost saving by a factor of three, which included the cost of the new tools. The features of the redesigned tail cone are shown in Figure 7. As an indication of the problems occurring with making the original design, it should be noted that extracting the rubber mandrels from inside each stiffener segment frequently resulted in the stiffener segment completely delaminating off the skin.

Sometimes, some of them could not be extracted at all, which meant that they remained on the aircraft, adding weight, and required replacement mandrels to be made before the next integrally stiffened tail cone could be laid up.

Figure 6 Features of the hollow-hat section bonded beaded composite stringer

Figure 7 Improved secondarily bonded design for large aircraft tail cone, of far lower cost than original co-cured design

There is a feature in the coarse first digital analysis of large structures whenever the member is modelled with a single element through the thickness that masks the existence of interfacial problems

between members. This is explained in Figures 8 and 9. Figure 8 identifies the weak resin layer that connects a continuous member, the skin, to further structure that does not extend for the full length of the member it is attached to. In this case, a doubler run-out is shown. *ALL* of the load in the second member *MUST* pass through the single layer of weak resin.

Figure 8 Identification of weak resin interface between composite members of structure

Figure 9 shows, at the top, how a typical finite element model of this would be created when this detail was only a small part of a much larger structure with many more features. There would be only one element representing both skin and doubler, and single elements for the adjacent unreinforced skin. There is no interface shown. This is perfectly acceptable for a first step to establish internal loads in a structure based on the stiffnesses of the elements of that structure. However, there is more than a need to merely decompose the loads and moments in each element in the coarse model into ply-by-ply stresses and strains. The second step in the analysis process, to perform local analyses of each portion using boundary conditions established by the first analysis, also needs to assess potential interfacial problems of the type shown in Figure 8. But there is no warning from the first coarse analysis about where they exist. This makes automated processing of interfacial problems extremely difficult. Figure 9 also includes, at the bottom, a more realistic model of the skin-doubler combination, but still with the skin and doubler rigidly connected to each other. There is no representation of the interface.

Figure 9 Inherent difficulty in modelling interfacial hot spots using finite-element analyses

Unfortunately, the model that is over-simplified less is still inadequate. It will predict a singularity at Points X because the model lacks a representation of a real flexible interface, be it part of the resin matrix or a discrete layer of adhesive. The singularity finally warns of, and locates, a potential structural weakness, but does nothing to *quantify* its severity. Only the inclusion of a discrete interlayer, as in Figure 10 would enable the real peak shear and interlaminar tension stresses to be estimated. Even then, not all digital analyses would eliminate the singularity (the interlayer may need to be modelled as a series of springs rather than solid elements – but, without the discrete interlayer, none of them could).

Flexible Layer Added Between Skin and Doubler Enables Relative Motion to Avoid Predicting Artificial Singularities at Ends of Doubler

Flexible interlayer needs to be modelled only between points A and B, because the skin and doubler strain together in the interior, A to A.

Figure 10 Need to include discrete interlayer in finite element model to be able to quantify finite peak interfacial stresses and strains

The complexity of a model to realistically represent the situation requires no many very small finite elements in the model that such analyses are simply not performed routinely. Instead, having been misled by the creation of an artificial singularity through using a still over-simplified model, it has been wrongly assumed that a fracture-mechanics approach is needed. That is how such details are analyzed today, when they are. Unfortunately, fracture mechanics analyses require the pre-existence of a starter crack, so it is still impossible to identify the loads needed to fail the matrix, there, in the absence of any pre-existing crack. Worse, numerical problems with computer codes require that the starter crack be quite large before the computer codes will actually run. So there is still no reliable analysis to establish when the matrix would fail under these circumstances, which are quite common. This is why the author feels strongly that the *ONLY* practical way around such potential problems is to design them out of the structures with constraints on design details which, from experience, will ensure that natural matrix failures simply do not occur.

The reason for including these actual cases of production problems with co-cured composite structures is to explain why it is so very important to be able to accurately predict premature matrix failures in composite laminates, which is impossible when their analysis, and the thinking behind the design, does not extend beyond the homogenized ply level. Fibre/polymer composite structures are already susceptible to accidental delaminations from impacts in service; such structures should not be compromised by design features that cause delaminations even without the need for impact damage. It is hoped that these same examples will illustrate the critical need to think of fibre/polymer composites as a combination of strong stiff fibres and a weak soft resin matrix to eliminate as many delaminations as possible through rational design. History shows that the composites fraternity has yet to reach that level of understanding.

2 THE CORRECT STEP-BY-STEP PROCESS FOR DIGITAL DESIGN OF FIBRE/POLYMER COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

The widespread use of the homogenized lamina misrepresentation of fibre/polymer composites for strengths instead of only well as stiffnesses (for which it is a valid assumption) has bred an almost complete lack of awareness of the inability of such theories to be able to accurately predict failures in the matrix that could precede the predicted failures in the fibres [3-4].

Once it is acknowledged that the fibres and resin matrix are separate quantities that may not fail simultaneously, it becomes necessary to establish the actual strain components in both materials, to make it possible to make scientific predictions about when each will fail. With only one exception, the longitudinal strain along the axis of the fibre, none of the strain components at the homogenized-lamina level of analysis is the same as in the constituents. How realistic should one expect predictions of failures in the matrix be when the only known strain component is the only one not involved in the prediction? Likewise, how realistic can predictions of failure in the matrix be when none of the residual thermal stresses that exist in the “homogenized lamina” when there are no terms whatever to account for their presence in a single ply that is free from all mechanical loads? The situation in regard to predicting failures in the fibres is not as bad, since failure is dominated by the longitudinal load component. This is why it was possible to develop useful empirical non-interactive fibre-failure criteria that could be applied at the homogenized lamina level of analysis, which have been the backbone of most of the design and analysis tools for fibre-polymer composites for at least the aerospace industry. But even those were found to be improved significantly when they were truncated in the tension-compression quadrants to allow for an interaction between longitudinal and transverse loads on the fibres; without such a truncation, the empirically predicted in-plane-shear strengths of laminates were far too high.

The unjustified, and physically unrealistic, assumption of homogeneity results in strength-prediction theories that totally lack the terms needed to quantify the intense residual thermal stresses *within* each ply that are caused by curing the resin at high temperature and operating at the structure at extremely cold high altitudes; these stresses in the matrix are simply ignored by analysis at the homogenized ply level. Only the thermal stresses (and equivalent strains) caused by laminating plies oriented in different directions are accounted for. This situation is compounded by the malpractice of conducting all large-scale testing at room temperature; the customary “compensation” for this effect is to add an increment of mechanical load, which causes the fibres to fail earlier while the possibility of encountering a matrix failure during the test is greatly diminished. Given the impracticality of carrying out all large-scale and complete airframe testing in a huge environmentally controlled chamber, the need to be able to analytically account for *ALL* the stresses and strains in the matrix is paramount. This requires an analysis tool that can be applied at the individual constituent level, i.e. the fibres and the resin matrix separately, each with its own separate failure criteria.

The complete analysis process required to be able to predict matrix failures in composite laminates is explained in Figure 11. The customary process stops prematurely, at the homogenized-lamina level, after the second step.

The digital-computer analysis of large composite aircraft structures begins with a coarse finite-element model with only one element across the thickness of the skins, for example. The properties for each such element are therefore homogenized at the laminate level. This first analysis is then post-processed, using lamination theory in reverse, decomposing each such laminate ply by ply into separate layers, each still having its own homogenized properties. The SIFT approach (explained in the next section) carries this process one step further, decomposing the lamina-level strains, ply by ply, into *constituent*-level strains and stresses. Only then is it possible to apply scientifically meaningful failure criteria. This necessary step, for matrix failures at least, is customarily ignored when analysis stops at the homogenized lamina level. Without this additional step, it is not possible to account for the differences between ply-level and constituent-level strains, or for residual thermal stresses (and

strains) in the matrix and, without these, it is not possible to *predict* (as distinct from empirically interpolating between test results) matrix failures. In other words, without this second post-processing step, which is customarily omitted because the plies are homogenized, it is simply not possible to mathematically predict matrix failures that might precede fibre failures, or to design composite structures that would *not* fail first in the matrix.

Figure 11 Progressively enhanced definitions of stresses and strains in composite laminates

An example of the micro-mechanical model needed to convert lamina-level strains into constituent-level strains is shown in Figure 12. This is what Gosse used as we developed SIFT, the mathematical model for which is explained in the next section.

With reference to the model in Figure 12, uniform unit lamina-level loads (or strains) in longitudinal tension and compression, transverse tension and compression, and in-plane or transverse shear, were applied in turn, with the unloaded exterior surfaces stress-free, which meant that they need not remain flat as the internal mid-planes did. The strains half-way along the element represented the interior of structural laminates. This model allowed the progressive drop-off in load in the fibres adjacent to free surfaces, and the associated build-up in interfacial load transfer between the fibres and resin to be quantified. A significant finding from these models was that the internal strains in both constituents correctly dropped to zero on the unloaded surfaces; these analyses converged with finer meshes without creating any of the usual artificial singularities; the peak strains were located a short distance off the free surfaces.

What the absence of the usual mathematically predicted artificial singularities in the matrix on the free surfaces with this level of analysis means is that it is possible to identify excessive blocking of parallel plies that would be prone to edge delaminations by analyses carried out early in the design process, to allow for corrections of the initial design. This is simply not possible with customary over-simplified analyses that stop at the homogenized lamina level and predict the creation of singular stresses and strains in the matrix there. These constituent-level analyses become unnecessary once the limits on

ply thickness have been established for each fibre/resin combination, for a standardized fibre volume fraction/

Figure 12 Micromechanical models to relate lamina and constituent-level strains

These models were later simplified by a suggestion from a colleague at the McDonnell Aircraft Company in St. Louis, who introduced the unit cell model depicted in Figure 13.

Figure 13 Unit cell model adopted for later sift micromechanical model

The unit-cell model produced all the same strain components in the interior of the element in Figure 12, losing only the ability to analyze edge effects. Both models were also used to evaluate the effects

of fibre volume fraction and fiber array, represented by square, diamond, and both horizontal and vertical hexagonal arrays. It was found that the difference between matrix strains at the constituent level of analysis were quite sensitive to the fibre volume fraction, but there was only a limited sensitivity to fibre array, which justified standardizing on the square array for the correlation between constituent-level strain components and those at the homogenized lamina level.

One of the attributes of the SIFT model is that most of the analyses need to be performed only once; the intrinsic fibre and resin properties are close to constant below the glass transition temperature for the resin, which should be above the highest operating temperature. The micromechanical strain enhancement factors vary primarily only with fibre volume fraction, which is normally a controlled quantity once a decision has been made to use a specific fibre/polymer combination. The SIFT model can, in fact, be (and has been) applied using a pre-populated array of strain-amplification factors, which have to be established only the once, enabling the third step in the analysis to be undertaken without needing new micromechanical analyses every time.

The issue of the effects of fibre array is actually irrelevant, as is explained later, because the lamina-level tests used to establish the in-situ fibre strengths each contain millions of fibres and millions of interstices between the fibres, so whatever the local fibre array might be, the measurement takes account of the actual random distributions of arrays.

The continuing need to use a constituent-level model to predict matrix failures in composite laminates is explained in detail in the body of this article. Only the strain along the axis of the fibres is common between the strain set in the constituents and the homogenized lamina; *all* other strain components, whether thermally induced or applied mechanically, are appreciably different. It was the common longitudinal fibre strain, in the fibres and in the unidirectional laminae, that formed the basis of all the successful empirical analysis models for fibre failures at the homogenized lamina level. (All well-designed composite structures were characterized by the absence of significant matrix failures until *after* the fibres were loaded to their full capabilities.)

3 FIBRE/POLYMER COMPOSITE FAILURE THEORY AT THE HETEROGENEOUS CONSTITUENT LEVEL

Having demonstrated from past experiences that there is a real need to be able to reliably and scientifically predict failures in the matrix of the composite that might precede failure of the fibres, attention is next focused on the features of the only theory known to the author to have been validated as capable of doing so. (Even so, some of the configurations encountered in composite designs remain to be analyzed to determine the relationship between the strains at the unidirectional lamina level and those in the individual fibre and resin matrix constituents, so there are opportunities to expand its application by constructing more micro-mechanical models.)

The basis of the SIFT (Strain Invariant Failure Theory), [5-6], composite failure model is that *all* solid materials can fail by *only* one of two mechanisms – dilatation and distortion. (The initial elastic distortional failures may or may not be followed by nonlinear further deformations before the material finally breaks up into pieces. Failure by dilation is instantly complete.) Therefore, these two mechanisms *must* apply to each of the fibre and polymer constituents of fibre/polymer composites. There are no other possibilities. These are intrinsic material properties that apply for all triaxial combinations of stress and strain. However, here, the focus is on laminated plate and shell structures. There are, therefore, four theoretically possible totally independent failure mechanisms available for fibre/polymer composites. Which if the four occurs first will vary between the states of biaxial tension, biaxial compression, and tension/compression, recognizing that these in-plane loads may cause stresses and strains in all three directions. The two equations covering these failure mechanisms are as follows.

Failure by dilatation is characterized by exceeding a critical value of the first strain invariant, J_1 , which is a very close approximation of the increase in volume for small strains. That is

$$J_1 = \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 \quad . \quad (1)$$

As an invariant, there is no difference between the sum of these orthogonal strains with different reference axes. These strain components are in the individual constituents; they are not the mathematical strains calculated at the homogenized lamina level.

Failure by distortion can be expressed by the shear strain equivalent to the well-known von Mises' shear stress

$$\gamma_{\text{crit}} = \sqrt{\frac{(\varepsilon_1' - \varepsilon_2')^2 + (\varepsilon_1' - \varepsilon_3')^2 + (\varepsilon_2' - \varepsilon_3')^2}{2}} \quad , \quad (2)$$

where the prime suffices denote the principal directions. For other sets of triaxial directions, a much more complicated formula must be generated, accounting for the three shear strains as well.

In theory, Hooke's Law could be used to convert Equation (2) to a more commonly used form in terms of stresses, instead of strains. It would not be quite as simple for isotropic materials, but doing so would not offer any advantage. However, carbon fibres are strongly orthotropic, and the stress-based equivalent of Equation (2) would be so complex as to be virtually unusable, even with a digital computer. Expressing distortional failures in terms of strains eliminates all such problems; Equation (2) applies equally to isotropic resin matrices and to orthotropic carbon fibres (as well as to isotropic glass fibres, of course).

For fibre/polymer composites, it is extremely difficult to apply compressive loads (at the lamina level) that cause distortional failures in the resin matrix, because of the internal residual thermal stresses caused by the stiff embedded fibres. So most matrix failures are caused by dilation. (It is not possible to cause failure by equal tri-axial compression.) Conversely, carbon and glass fibres fail most of the time by distortion. Gosse and Christiansen could find no way to make carbon fibres fail by dilatation, which is not a problem because it simply means that that theoretical failure mechanism can be omitted from the stress analysis for the fibres. Experience with typical aerospace carbon-epoxy materials has shown that the fibres fail predominantly by distortion, which the author called shear when he first recognized this in 1983 (generating a lot of hostility from the composites experts of the day), while the resin matrix failed predominantly by dilation, which Gosse recognized sometime in the early to mid-1990s (meeting similar resistance).

It was the author who first understood the need to predict failure at the constituent level; initially, Gosse was reluctant to venture into the field of micromechanics, having seen the rather brutal dismissal of the works of the pioneering micro-mechanicians by the advocates for terminating the structural analyses at the artificially homogenized laminate level. However, once he understood the need for it, he became an enthusiastic supporter and all of his great skills in digital structural analysis enabled the process to be completed. What is significant about this collaboration is that each author had independently made great strides in developing the analysis tools necessary to be able to *predict* all possible failures in composites, without first knowing the answer, but neither was ever likely to complete the task on his own. It was the combining of skills and resources that led to success. Tribute should also be paid to the careful experimental work of a colleague at Boeing Seattle, Steve Christensen, who developed the non-standard robust test coupons needed to properly characterize the lamina-level properties that the standard test coupons were incapable of doing.

Figure 14 shows a graphical three-dimensional representation of the SIFT failure model on the strain plane, with the dilatational failures on the matrix truncating the distortional failure of the fibres.

Figure 14 SIFT model for characterization of strengths of fibers *and* matrix in terms of strain invariants

Some of the fibre and matrix elastic constants used for the SIFT model can be measured by tests on the individual constituents, but most of the strengths need to be deduced from a specific set of coupons selected to yield the most reliable values for each property needed. One need for this process is that it is impossible to create the conditions for failure of the unreinforced matrix by dilatation through mechanical loads alone; the intense tensile residual thermal stresses and strains created from curing the resin at high temperature and operating the laminate at room temperatures or the very negative temperatures at high altitude are needed to create a set of strains whereby failure by dilatation can be achieved prior to failure by distortion (which could be measured in isolation). Totally different coupon geometry is needed to create a distortional in-situ failure in the resin matrix. Failure of the fibres, measured as an in-situ property requires a longitudinal tension test but, the same value is valid for longitudinal compression as well, since the distortion is equal in both cases. Details of the specific robust coupons are available in some of Gosse's publications; they are not germane to the issues discussed here other than to remark that their development was not considered to be finalized until it became impossible to demonstrate higher strengths. All of these robust coupons were much longer and much thicker than the standard test coupons; some of the measured strengths were so much higher than measured on the standard coupons (particularly in the case of transverse tension) that one should seriously consider establishing new standards. Cost-reduction during testing, and the desire to be able to compare the results of different investigations, should never become such a priority as to handicap the use of a material in real structures.¹

One of the most significant findings of the early constituent-level micromechanical analyses was that peak dilatational conditions in the matrix were likely to occur in only two locations; the inter-fibre location where parallel fibers were the closest to each other, and the interstitial resin-rich locations

¹ The standard adhesively bonded lap-shear coupon is perhaps the best example of this phenomenon. It makes an ideal quality-assurance coupon, but the apparent "strength" measured is not only useless in the design process, it is potentially dangerously misleading in the context of a bond strength being predicted to be the bonded area times this supposedly uniform adhesive shear strength.

where the fibres were the greatest distance apart, allowing the local blob of resin to try to shrink more than the surrounding resin. Knowing where to seek peak conditions in the resin matrix should have permitted a reduction in the complexity of the analysis, but the micromechanical analyses of the unit cells was so simple and quick that this opportunity was ignored. In any event, the critical location in the matrix was not always the same between strains caused by mechanical loads and by internal thermal loads. (Ref. [5] contains illustrative results of such micromechanical analyses and far more information about the capabilities of the SIFT model than are needed to address the issues raised here. It even includes a demonstration of how a lamina-level failure envelope can be created from the constituent properties.) Some exploratory micromechanical analyses of the interface between adjacent plies of fibres in different directions, or of the cross-over point within a single layer of woven tows of fibres reveal a curious prediction, which makes sense when considered. At the cross-over point, the resin is compressed strongly in the thickness direction perpendicular to the layers of the laminate because of the intense shrinkage of the interstitial blobs of resin within the laminate between the cross-over points. A world of important information about the strains in the resin matrix was revealed by the SIFT model that could never have been predicted at the homogenized lamina level. This is precisely what has been withheld from designers and analysts by the past fixation on lamina-level analysis alone for the so-called composite materials.

4 COMMENTS ON THE USE OF FRACTURE-MECHANICS ANALYSES IN PLACE OF CONTINUUM MECHANICS TO DEAL WITH MATRIX FAILURES IN COMPOSITES

The major focus on matrix failures in fibre/polymer composite laminates nowadays is on delaminations, which are analyzed using fracture mechanics. Again, there is a potential problem of applying a theory developed for a homogeneous material to a heterogeneous combination of one strong and one weak constituent. But the greatest drawback to the customary fracture mechanics analyses for composite laminates is that the damage must already be substantial before such analyses can be made to work numerically. These analyses are intended to identify the size of delaminations that will not grow in service, which implies intent to minimize expensive and frequent non-destructive inspections to identify delaminations that are difficult to find visually, and a further goal of not needing to repair the delamination immediately. The tolerable damage sizes are verified by testing at room temperature. The author would suggest that this is not a realistic environment for such tests, since it addresses only possible growth under mechanical loads. The author's experiences suggest that even small delaminations, left unrepaired, would grow under the freeze-thaw environmental cycle. Damage in a composite laminate that is left unrepaired until the next scheduled down time (as is common with some aluminum alloys that exhibit slow crack growth at quite long lengths) risks almost certain further growth, even without further application of mechanical loads. If the damage in the laminate is exposed to the atmosphere, it will fill with condensate whenever the aircraft descends from high altitude; this will then freeze and expand every time the aircraft climbs back to the sub-zero high-altitude cruise environment, spreading the initial damage, flight by flight, in a manner that cannot be simulated by mechanical loads at room temperature.²

The environmental degradation from the freeze-thaw cycle has already occurred widely with the Kevlar/Nomex honeycomb panels that had to be replaced by fiberglass-skinned panels fleet-wide,

² This separation between the effects of mechanical loads and corrosion is particularly evident for metallic military aircraft, in which the pitting from corrosion occurs during the many hours the aircraft sit on the ground, unloaded, while fatigue cracks grow during flight in a non-corrosive environment at high altitude. Fatigue testing should thus not be conducted in a corrosive environment; it should be conducted *after* conditioning to simulate the corrosion damage. (The author is indebted to a colleague, L Molent, of DSTO in Fishermen's Bend, Victoria, Australia, for explaining this.) Likewise, in the case of composite aircraft that are bolted together, lightning strikes decrease the fatigue life with respect to virgin structures. Mechanical testing of composite panels containing impact damage needs to be combined with periodic freeze-thaw cycles to be realistic. Testing to realistically represent in-service conditions can be quite a challenge.

because the porous skins created by large bundles of Kevlar fibres that the resin would not wet allowed water to pass through the skins and accumulate in the honeycomb cells [1]. The water from previous flights would freeze as the aircraft flew at high altitude and could not thaw out as fast as the external temperature built up as the aircraft descended to land. Even if it could have, it was trapped in innumerable small cavities from which it could not drain away, so it accumulated until the cells were full. On early flights after a frosty night, condensate would appear over all the thin-skin faces, which logically should have warmed up first, and be absent over all the places on top of thick structure, which should have warmed up slowest. It was ice in the honeycomb cells that caused this abnormal situation. This phenomenon was so reliable that it was used by the mechanics for the Concorde aircraft, immediately after landing, to indicate areas of delaminations that needed to be repaired.

5 THE DISTORTIONS OF STATISTICAL DATA CAUSED BY THE FALSE ASSUMPTION OF HOMOGENEITY

The measured strengths of fibre/polymer composite laminae, which only rarely are the same as are developed within laminates, are affected by two sources of variables; material variations in the fibres and resin matrix constituents, which are extremely small and no greater than those associated with typical metals, and those larger variables associated with manufacturing of the material and, in the case of test coupons, the design of the test coupons and the testing techniques. The customary decision to pretend that so-called composite materials are homogeneous at the lamina level has led to the accumulation of test data at that level, rather than at the level of individual fibre and resin constituents. This, in turn, has made it all but impossible to associate variations in measured strengths with the cause of such variations, be it in one of the constituent materials or from any cause *not* related to material variability. This limitation in regard to differentiating between different causes of variability is far more serious than is commonly recognized – because no one has evaluated any alternative series of tests. It *should* have affected how measured composite-material properties are interpreted statistically to establish approved values for design and analysis.

While the author was serving as the company representative on what used to be called MIL-HDBK-17, which is now referred to as the Composite Materials Handbook, at the request of the FAA, the government statisticians from NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology) discovered some anomalies in the sets of test data they were evaluating. These irregularities undermined the fundamental basis of the document, which was to establish composite material properties that any manufacture of composite structures could use, provided that it carefully followed the defined process specification under which the reference test data had been created. The data showed clearly that the variation in properties that could be associated with issues that were *intrinsic to the material* were smaller than the variation that had to be associated with the *manufacture and testing* of the coupons. The distinction was clouded by the use of standard test coupons that were unsuitable for such strong stiff materials that were brittle and sensitive to delaminations. This was recognized at the time, and new more reliable test coupons were designed for unidirectional tension and compression, but there was still a long way to go to achieve the consistently higher strengths attained by the very long thick (robust) coupons developed to validate the SIFT composite failure model. (There is an inherent problem associated with introducing new coupons to produce higher more consistent strengths; doing so effectively invalidates the earlier data accumulated from inferior test coupons or test techniques. However, not doing so imposes a handicap on the use of composite materials.)

The greatest source of confusion in satisfying the goals of MIL-HDBK-17 is the assumption that the combination of discrete fibres and the resin matrix created a homogeneous material. This assumption means that each test coupon represents a *single* data point. This model requires many individual tests to create a data bank large enough to be interpreted statistically (with mean values and A- and B-allowables). The reality that each coupon contains a *million* or more fibres and a similar number of resin interstices between them means that the sample size in regard to an individual test coupon is on the order of a million; under this interpretation, only the *mean* measured strength is statistically

significant (provided that only the best coupon designs are used, to eliminate as many variations due to non-materials effects as possible). This is explained in Figure 15.

Figure 15 Explanation of true sample sizes for fibre/polymer composite test coupons

This, in turn, means that any individual test result that is significantly lower than the highest in a series of nominally identical tests is lower because of variations necessarily *unrelated* to intrinsic fibre and resin properties – and that only the highest individual test result in a series of nominally identical tests is a valid characterization of the true lamina-level strength of the “composite” material. None of the presumed reference strengths presented in MIL-HDBK-17 or the later Composites Materials Handbook is consistent with this heterogeneous model. More importantly, the greater scatter between test coupons made from a single panel than between coupons made from different batches of pre-pregs calls into question the whole notion of universal lamina-level properties that all participants in a multi-supplier program can adopt simply by using the same common process specification. Even if the constraints in the specification are satisfied, uncontrolled variables such as the manufacturing environment and the time elapsed between successive steps in composite curing and adhesive bonding (the latter of which *IS* tightly controlled for most metal-bond products until the primer has been applied) can have serious effects on the quantity and strength of the product produced.

Aircraft design and manufacturing companies are free to apply their own knock-down factors to measured strengths to create whatever level of conservatism they want, but whatever their policy, it will be more reliable if based on the most reliable nominal properties. Likewise, validating the use of outside suppliers requires more than adhering to a common process specification; it should also require a demonstration that each supplier can produce composite laminates consistent with the *intrinsic* lamina-level strengths, can make and test the coupons so as to demonstrate *consistent* strengths, and continues to do so during the entire production program. Meeting any lower targets is inconclusive. (Out-sourcing the coupon testing to a lower-cost specialized laboratory would not be acceptable, either.)

This is no trivial matter. For one block of data submitted to the MIL-HDBK-17 organization, the aircraft manufacturer, the pre-preg manufacturer, and an independent test laboratory could not make and test statistically equivalent coupons when starting from the very *same* roll of pre-preg. This was a most powerful indicator of the true sources of variability in lamina-level “properties”.

6 CUSTOMARILY OVERLOOKED DIFFERENCES BETWEEN INTERLAMINAR AND INTRALAMINAR RESIDUAL THERMAL STRAINS IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES

Artificially homogenizing the individual plies in a multi-directional laminate does not eliminate prediction of *ALL* of the residual thermal stresses in the resin matrix; only the worst of them. (The thermally induced stresses in the fibres are on the same order as those in the matrix, but are only an insignificant fraction of the intrinsic mechanical strength of the fibres, while they are a large fraction of the intrinsic strength of typical resin matrices.) Prior to lamination, the homogenized model would predict absolutely *zero* residual thermal stresses within each ply in isolation. The homogenized laminae have much greater transverse coefficients of thermal expansion than along the length of the fibres, so combinations of plies stacked in various directions in a panel will develop roughly equal and opposite uniform stresses within each ply, dropping to zero at the free edges of the panel, with infinite interlaminar shear stresses around the perimeter of the panel to enforce compatibility of deformations. This is treated as a singularity at this level of modelling, for both thermally and mechanically induced internal ply loads. If a small portion of the resin matrix were modelled as a flexible interlayer between the plies, the interlaminar shear stresses in the later will build up from zero in the interior to a finite value around the perimeter, as is explained in Figure 16. The singularity would then disappear, which confirms that the ones that are predicted are mathematical aberrations caused by an insufficient level of detail in the homogenized model. (This seems to have been overlooked in most of the literature on free-edge stresses and strains in fibre/polymer composite laminates, in the sense that such analyses were not replaced by more realistic analyses using a model with flexible interfaces of small but not precisely zero thickness to eliminate the singularities. The one exception that the author is aware of is discussed in [1].)

Figure 16 Artificial singularities created by omission of flexible interlayers from model of composite laminates

The net result of this over-simplification of the model for multi-directional laminates, because of the homogenization of each ply and the omission of a flexible interlayer between such plies, has been the questionable application of fracture-mechanics methods to problems where there would be no need for

them if the model had been sufficiently realistic. Unlike the situation of a through-crack in a metal plate, there are no singularities in either the transverse-tension or transverse-shear stresses at free edges of fibre/polymer composite laminates, regardless of the mechanical loads or thermal environment. This statement covers both interlaminar shear stresses, and interlaminar tension stresses, until after small cracks or delaminations have been mathematically inserted there to “justify” the use of fracture mechanics analyses for this class of problems. The irony is that fracture-mechanics analyses require a large delamination for the computer programs to run, so that they are unable to quantify the initial effects of imposed defects on free surfaces of fibre/polymer composites anyway. Even the well-known case of theoretical singularities at the ends of adhesively bonded joints has been shown to be a mathematical aberration, rather than a reality, by proper modelling of the adhesive layer (both by closed-form analyses and finite-element analysis). The real distribution of the adhesive shear stress, which is physically equivalent to an abrupt ply drop in a composite laminate, has the form shown in Figure 17, when variations through the thickness of the adhesive layer (or flexible resin layer) are accounted for. In reality, the peak adhesive shear stress develops very close to the end of one adherend (the abrupt ply drop-off in composite laminates), not right on the free surface.

Fig. 17 The Actual Interlaminar Shear-Stress Distribution at the Abrupt Termination of Stiff Composite Members

The initial digital analyses performed by Gosse during the validation of the SIFT failure model, once we had agreed on the physics of the situation, always exhibited the absence of singularities on the free edges of the element when using the model shown in Figure 12. This is because the resin surrounding the fibres acted as the flexible layer transferring load between them.

By definition, *if* a fibre/polymer ply really were truly homogeneous, it would be stress free in the absence of mechanical loads, no matter what the operating temperature. In reality, however, the combination of fibres and resin would be stress free only prior to curing. At the start of the cross-linking process, the resin would be a liquid. As it cures, and is transformed into a solid, it *tries* to shrink because of the change in phase; but this is resisted, because the fibres are so much stiffer than the cured resin. As the cured resin contracts, the ply thickness will decrease but, even so, tensile hoop stresses will develop in the resin around each fibre. Far greater stresses will develop along the length of the fibre (carbon fibres have an almost zero longitudinal coefficient of thermal expansion and a transverse stiffness far less than along the length). Then, once the curing was complete, and each composite lamina was allowed to cool to room temperature, to be operated later at the sub-zero temperatures at high altitude, steadily increasing the intraply stresses in the resin. (There would be matching compressive stresses in the fibres, but these would be insignificant in comparison with the relatively enormous longitudinal fibre strength.) The surface of each ply, if it were cured in isolation,

would be stress free, but the resin would be riddled with residua thermally and chemically induced stresses. However, because of the inappropriate assumption that each ply was homogeneous for the purposes of analysis, not even the existence of these stresses could be established, let alone their magnitude.

The same singularities in stresses and strains that are predicted at the edges of composite panels (both unidirectional and multi-directional laminates) arise when the effects of mechanical loads are analyzed using assumed homogenized individual plies with no flexible interlayers between them. The model is just as inappropriate then as for thermally induced loads, even though few composites analysts would acknowledge that this is so.

This means that this detail in the analysis does not even qualify for analysis by fracture mechanics models, even though the advocates for such analyses have convinced the regulators to impose a “requirement” that it is necessary to *assume* that there are starter cracks there. Otherwise, it would not even be possible to apply such analyses there, and the presumption that the singularities they believe to be real would be exposed as merely the artificial result of over-simplified modelling that needed to be refined. In this case, the belatedly imposed mandated standard starter-crack crack length was needed to legitimize this malpractice and to ensure that all the erroneously predicted results were comparable. (This criticism is not intended to be applied in the context of real delaminations caused by impact damage, anywhere in the structure. Delaminations from impact to composite laminates are so complicated that there are no alternative analyses available. However, it needs to be noted that the reality of a real crack growing through a transverse ply until it is arrested by the fibres in adjacent longitudinal plies and probably then spreading as an in-plane delamination is so localized that neither continuum mechanics nor fracture mechanics analyses could be applied routinely then. The author does not know how best to analyze delaminations in composite laminates precisely, so his approach would be the design with thin plies, thoroughly interspersed, so that such damage would not spread unless it failed instantly after damage because the damage was too large for the applied loads. If the plies were thin enough and their directions well interspersed, it might well be possible to eliminate barely visible impact damage (BVID) and replace it with a limited choice between either no damage or an only possible alternative of clearly visible damage needing prompt repair without delay. Both of these alternatives would be far easier to implement in service than not knowing whether or not there is invisible internal damage and therefore having to assume that there always is.)

A series of tests at the Douglas Aircraft Company, in the late 1970s or early 1980s [2], sheds considerable light on the design options available to eliminate delaminations as an in-service problem. A series of quasi-isotropic (0/+45/90/-45)_s laminates was made with single 0.005-inch (0.1 mm) plies, two parallel plies stacked together, and 4 and 8 plies at a time. Otherwise, the panels were identical. The panel with the greatest blocking delaminated into essentially unidirectional wafers during cooling down after curing at 350°F (180°C) before it could even be removed from the autoclave, as is explained in Figure 18. This series of tests, and more, confirmed the design rule of no more than 4 such blocked plies adjacent to a 45 deg. change in fibre direction, and no more than 2 such plies blocked adjacent to a 90 deg. change in fibre direction. Modern resins are far tougher than the first generation, so the tolerable minimum ply thickness will be slightly greater, but the induced stresses will be much the same, so the problem of thermally induced stresses and strains that are omitted from contemporary composite analyses remains. These thermally induced stresses and strains limit practical composite designs to not deviate excessively from quasi-isotropic laminates, reinforcing the same limitations enforced by the inclusion of bolted joints in the structure. (Bolted joints cannot easily be avoided if the structure is thick enough because of the limit on the strength of bonded joints or the need for in-service repairs of thick damaged composite structures.)

The bottom line on the conventional simplifying assumption that it is acceptable for laminate strength prediction, rather than just stiffness prediction, is that doing so increases the likelihood of unanticipated premature failures in the resin matrix before the fibres were predicted to fail. This problem is aggravated because, if it is overlooked during the design stage of product development, it is

unlikely to be uncovered before it is exposed during full-scale testing that was intended to confirm that there were *no* such problems, *not* to discover mistakes made earlier. Worse yet, it may not become apparent until the cyclic environmental exposures are encountered in service.

Figure 18 Edge delaminations, or worse, caused by excessive blocking of parallel plies

3 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The time for ceasing the malpractice of terminating the analysis and design processes for composite structures at the homogenized lamina level arrived some decades ago. The excuse that there was no practical reliable analysis model available, for those people who at least recognized the deficiencies inherent in this practice, disappeared with the advent of the SIFT (Strain Invariant Failure Theory) that was completed in 2001.

The failure to carry the analysis one step further to quantify the strains in the resin matrix, in particular, before specifying the loads at which failures in the matrix precede failure in the fibres in such a way as to prevent resistance to any higher loads has led to an almost complete reliance of full-scale testing to certify large composite aircraft that will not diminish until the analyses are no longer stopped one or two steps before the end.

Understanding *how* fibre/polymer composites behave will *never* become widespread when the assessment is made at the homogenized ply level, rather than at the discrete fibre and polymer constituent level. Internal residual thermal stresses and strains that exist in discrete fibre and matrix constituents cannot be characterized inside an artificially homogenized individual ply. Apparent singularities at the edges of laminated composite panels, abrupt stiffener terminations, and the ends of splice plates or doublers, disappear when over-simplified models are corrected by the addition of flexible interlayers.

There is a long history of unanticipated premature failures in the matrix causing delays in development programs and substantial additional costs. Solving such problems empirically, by tests alone, provides no impetus to develop and/or implement new analyses that would preclude further such problems in future products.

The problem caused by failure to identify potential matrix failures before the design is complete, so that prompt redesign can eliminate them, is that the high cost of fixing such problems later, particularly if they are not recognized until after series production has commenced, discourages fixing such problems, resulting in inefficient structures and supplemental inspections in progress that decrease the time such products can be used to generate revenue for the operators.

There is a reliable, and validated, alternative approach to avoiding matrix failures that has worked most of the time when advanced composites were in their infancy. This empirical approach placed constraints on the number of parallel plies that could be stacked together (effectively the maximum ply thickness), how many plies of various orientations could be dropped off at a time and how thoroughly the plies in various directions needed to be interspersed. Sadly, with the passage of time and the progressively greater blind reliance on whatever output the computer provided, this wisdom has been lost. Resistance from the advocates for composite structures against constraints that prevented them from “optimizing” fibre layups (using failure theories that failed to require consideration of potential matrix failures) has inhibited its rediscovery.

The need to never terminate stiffeners short of the edges of panels has been over-ridden by a desire to minimize *estimated* production costs. In the same vein, the need to taper the ends of splice plates and doublers to soften the shear load transfer there and to minimize induced interlaminar tension stresses has been overlooked because the weakness of the resin matrix is not as apparent in homogenized models as in heterogeneous models with separate fibres and resin.

Since the predicted strengths from interactive homogenized failure theories, using *measured* transverse ply properties, were unacceptable to the notion that fibre-polymer composites would one day supplant the further use of metallic structures, the technique was developed of replacing the measured transverse ply properties with arbitrary different values that yielded more acceptable predicted laminate strengths, the critical importance of establishing *accurate* scientific predictions of matrix failures went unrecognized by all but a small minority of composite practitioners. This must have made it seem that there was no need for accurate predictions of matrix failures.

The purpose of this article is to provoke a thorough assessment of whether or not it is necessary to be able to scientifically predict matrix failures that would prevent the fibres in composite laminates from achieving their full load-carrying capability. The author has sought to explain why he believes it *IS* necessary, by recording some of the many past and current penalties incurred by not doing so. He has also indicated that doing so is finally straightforward, since the SIFT composite failure theory was developed. If this challenge is not accepted, the alternative of developing *and enforcing*, a complete set of laminate and design constraints needs to be adopted, as a minimum response to a very real problem that holds back the successful applications of composites, because there are far too many re-occurrences of the *same* known failure mechanisms that occurred in the past. The two most frequent design defects that need to be eliminated are abrupt terminations in stiffeners short of the edge of panels and the blocking together of too many parallel fibres.

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